

RUBBER FORMING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE PARTS FOR THE EAGLET RUDDER

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SUMMARY: The purpose of this paper is to give practical information on the rubber forming of thermoplastic composite parts for a movable. This includes technical details of the production of rubber moulds, things that should be taken into account during the design phase of tooling and at last, the equipment needed to produce the parts. The production of a monolithic thermoplastic movable was a new challenge in the development of these materials and their applications. The feasibility of the production of large structural aircraft components of carbon-reinforced thermoplastics in the future will be shown. In this perspective, the press forming of large structural parts is also discussed.

KEYWORDS: rubber forming, mould design, silicone rubber, press, blankholder, rudder, ribs.

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic composites are being used for their cost efficient process; one of these processes is rubber forming. Rubber forming is used to form parts for a thermoplastic composite rudder for the Eaglet, a full-composite 2-seater aircraft (figure 1).

The rudder of the Eaglet was redesigned from a thermoset sandwich structure to a thermoplastic multi-rib structure, leading to a weight reduction of approximately 40%.

Figure 1: Eaglet aircraft, the rudder is encircled

Figure 2: exploded view of the rudder

The multi-rib concept consists of a skin, seven ribs, spar, leading edge and some caps and ribs to close the structure (see figure 2). The skin was thermo folded. The ribs, spar, leading edge and the closing ribs were rubber formed, the lower and upper end cap are planned to be infused with RIM technology [6]. All parts are welded together where possible, making use of both resistance and ultrasonic welding processes [3].

First, the material and equipment used are mentioned in this paper. Thereafter, design rules for metal tooling are given and design aspects for the rubber tooling are discussed. The production of all the rubber moulds for every part is explained, where after positive net-shape forming of ribs is described and the considerations to choose either negative or positive forming are listed. Furthermore, the process parameters, used for the forming of carbon reinforced PEI are given and the press forming of the larger parts is highlighted separately. At last all the work is concluded.

MATERIALS AND EQUIPMENT

The material used to produce the rudder was continuous carbon fibre reinforced PEI from Ten Cate Advanced Composites (Cetex), with a lay-up of $\pm 45/0/90/\pm 45$, so 3 plies with a total thickness of 0,9 mm. The fabric used was a 5 harness satin weave.

For the press forming of ribs 2-6, horn rib and horn spar, a small 20-tons Alfamatic press was used. The test set-up is shown in figure 3 and exists of a Watlow infrared heater and a pneumatic cylinder to transport the panel. The cylinder automatically pulls the infrared panel back after a certain time. The heating time was calibrated with a dummy laminate with thermocouples inside.

Figure 3: left) test set-up 20-tons Alfamatic right) 400 tons Fontijne press

A 400 tons Fontijne press (see figure 3) was used to form the spar, leading edge and rib 1. The press exists of two infrared panels with an infrared temperature sensor and a fast transport system. The press can apply sufficient pressure to form parts of 1650 mm x 500 mm.

Blanks were dried in ovens at 150°C for at least 4 hours, prior to forming. This significantly decreases the void content in the parts, since PEI contains 1.3 % of water in equilibrium.

Trimming of the parts was mainly done with a band saw and a sanding belt machine.

RUBBER FORMING IN PRACTICE

Rubber forming is based on the principle that the thermoplastic resin melts and can be formed and reconsolidated.

Design Rules for Metal Tooling

The design of good tooling is the most important part of the rubber forming trajectory of a product. Firstly, it has to be determined whether the dimensional tolerances of the product should be at the inside or outside of the product. This choice determines in fact the way of rubber forming, positive or negative, where positive forming means that a positive metal tool is used.

In case of negative forming, the forces on the metal tool can become extremely high. When the mould cavity has undercuts or a section of the tool is too small to mill, the metal tool sometimes has to be produced out of two halves that can be bolted together. Especially in this case, the designer must be aware of the high forming forces. In case of positive forming, the negative rubber mould must be positioned in a metal case.

Steel tools are preferred over aluminium tools, since steel has a lower specific heat than aluminium. This means that the composite cools down more slowly when touching the steel tool. When the composite cools down locally prior to forming, this could prevent the deforming mechanisms of the fabric, which could result in poor part quality at certain sections. However, the leading edge tool was very difficult to mill and, therefore, made of aluminium because of cost issues.

Design Aspects Rubber Tooling

The rubber used for the forming of the Eaglet parts was Silastic M, a Dow Corning silicone rubber with a shore A hardness of 56. Silicone rubber must be used since the processing temperature of the material lies around 340°C. Silicone rubber can withstand these temperatures very shortly. Research has been performed to the influence of the hardness of the rubber on the behaviour. A silicone tool with a shore A of 25 cannot be used if details like sharp edges have to be pressed. To obtain good quality details in a rubber formed part, a high shore A of 70-80 has to be used, however, the shape of the rubber tool must then be perfectly optimised, since the deformations are much smaller. Therefore, Silastic M with a medium shore A hardness was used.

Rubber forming tests with a U-beam shape showed that the shape of the rubber has a very high impact on the pressure distribution over the part. In case of the U-beam, a rubber mould with the same shape as the metal resulted in a pressure distribution as shown in figure 4a. There is no pressure in the corners of the beam as can be concluded from figure 5, where a press formed U-beam with this rubber mould concept is shown. It was found that ridges on the corners of the rubber improve the pressure distribution in this case (see also figure 5). The same results were found by Robroek [5]. Since many parts that are press formed for the rudder, have the same cross sectional area as the U-beam, the rubber moulds for these parts were produced with ridges with the dimensions given.

A good way to produce a rubber tool is to use the existing metal tool as a casting shape. In the metal tool, plies of wax with specified thickness are applied and the wax is formed into the

desired shape while heating it with a hot air blower. The rubber is casted through an MDF plate with a step in hole diameter (see figure 6). Once cured, it is fixed to the MDF and can easily be clamped to the press platens. The MDF will ensure that the rubber is enclosed during forming.

Figure 4a and b) A rubber mould with the same shape as the metal mould (a), tends to deform as shown in (b)

Figure 4c and d) Deformation of the same rubber mould as 4a) with ridges.

Figure 5: Left) Press formed Carbon/PPS U-beam with rubber mould as shown in figure 4a. Right) Press formed Carbon/PPS U-beam with rubber mould as shown in figure 4c.

Figure 6: Left) MDF plate with different hole diameter where the rubber is moulded through, right) Once cured, the rubber is fixed to the MDF.

Rubber tool production for the Eaglet rudder

For the manufacturing of the ribs of the Eaglet rudder, positive rubber forming is used. The tools for the ribs 2-5 are shown in figure 7. The horn rib tools and the tools for rib 6 are similar. The rubber moulds for the production of the spar and the leading edge are shown in figures 12 and 13 respectively.

To reduce the manufacturing costs, the same casing was used for the moulds of rib 2-6 and the horn rib. Bee wax with a thickness of 1.0 mm was applied to the vertical sides of the metal moulds, in order to compensate for the material thickness. Figure 8 shows how the rubber was moulded.

Figure 7: Rib mould press forming tools

The strips of 2 mm are to ensure that the rib will be fully pressurized. Surfaces a and b (see figure 9) will first make contact during forming. After the press travels 2 mm extra, surface c will contact surface d and the rubber will be fully enclosed, after which a hydrostatic pressure is build-up on the rib.

Figure 8: Set-up used to mould the rubber for the ribs

Figure 9: Left) steel rib tool fixed to a steel plate, Right) Cured rubber mould in the casing

The rubber mould for the spar was produced with ridges of 2,5 mm high. To produce the mould with ridges, bee wax with a thickness of 2.0 mm was applied as shown in figure 10. A clearance of 7 mm from the flanges was used and the wax was beveled to obtain a smooth transition from the ridges to the flat area. A smooth transition is important for the part quality. Figure 11 shows what occurred when the wax was not beveled. Since the edges of the rubber mould are 2,5 mm higher, the total height of the rubber mould had to be increased with 2 mm to be able to fully pressurize the flanges of the spar. The rubber mould is shown in figure 12.

Figure 10: Spar mould cavity (top view). The coloured area marks the area where bee wax was applied.

Figure 11: Discontinuities in the spar due to rubber ridges that were not beveled.

Figure 12: Rubber spar mould

The leading edge has an undercut, which may lead to release difficulties. However, the rubber can deform as much as to fill the gap that is created between rubber and metal. This gap is needed to make the rubber fit into the mould cavity during forming and was created by applying aluminum strips of 1 mm thick (\approx material thickness) during casting of the rubber, as shown in figure 13a. The double curved section of the leading edge is in fact part of the end cap. However, it was decided to press it onto the leading edge too, to decrease the spring back effects in the part. Since this section also has an undercut, wax was applied as shown in figure 13b. The wax at the other side of the tool was applied to create spacing for expansion of the rubber mould once it becomes hot. The result is shown in figure 13c.

Figure 13: Production of the rubber mould for the leading edge. a) Alu strips to cast a rubber that fits into the cavity; b) Places where wax was applied; c) final rubber mould.

Since the rubber mould produced to press form the spar appeared to give excellent results, this concept was also used for the rib 1-mould end the horn spar. This means rubber ridges with the same dimensions were applied. The products produced with these moulds were directly satisfying.

Process Parameters

The most important process parameters for rubber forming are the laminate temperature (T_{mat}), the mould temperature (T_{mould}), pressure (p) and press time (t). For all products, the parameters were the same:

T_{mat}	=	340°C +/- 10°C
T_{mould}	=	180°C
p	=	60 bar
t	=	30 sec

In the 20-tons Alfamatic press, the laminate temperature was calibrated with a dummy laminate with thermocouples inside. A certain heating time to achieve 340°C was found and this time was set for all ribs. Next to the time, the distance to the infrared panel was constant too. The heating time for the parts pressed in the 400-tons press was calibrated with an infrared sensor. The steel moulds were electrically heated with a thermocouple feedback.

POSITIVE NET-SHAPE FORMING OF RIBS

Ribs 2–6 and the horn rib were rubber formed using the method of net-shape forming. This means blanks were precut to size. This was done with a bandsaw but could easily be automatised by using high precision techniques like waterjet cutting. The precut blank is then positioned on top of a steel rib mould with positioning pins that are pressed into the metal tool during forming (see figure 14). The material is heated by an infrared heater that travels over the blank. Once the desired temperature is reached, the rib is pressed with a negative rubber mould. The position of the pins is dependent on the dimensions of the rib mould and is modeled in ICAD [2].

Net-shape forming can only be used when the laminate thickness is small (<1mm), since one-sided heating is needed and heating thick laminates from one side will lead to a large temperature differential through the thickness. In order to position the blank precisely it must be positioned on top of the metal tool and therefore double sided heating cannot be used.

Figure 14: Rib mould with positioning pins.

The advantage of net-shape forming is that the pressed part does not need to be trimmed afterwards, but precutting is done on a flat laminate, with ease of handling. In addition, the lead-time between part production and assembly is kept short. A disadvantage is that the outsides of the ribs have a poor surface quality due to the contact with the rubber. The rubber presses the matrix in between the fibres. Since the outsides of the flanges have to be welded to the skin, the poor surface quality might cause preliminary short-circuiting due to applied pressure when welding carbon. However, resistance welding of the ribs to the skin with the method used by Van Dongen [7] was successful. Another disadvantage of positive forming is that it becomes more difficult to apply pressure to vertical parts of the product.

FORMING OF LARGE PARTS

Rubber forming of large parts is one of the challenges for the future. Since high pressures of approximately 60 bars are used to form the parts, large presses have to be used. In addition, more complex tooling is required to transport and position the large blanks.

Since rib 1 is larger than the other ribs, it could not be pressed in the small 20-tons Alfamatic press. The 400-tons press was used and therefore double-sided heating was used, which also meant the part could not be formed the same way as the other ribs. Negative forming was used, since the rubber tool can be simplified in that case. The part is shown in figure 15.

Figure 15: Rib 1

Figure 16: Complete set-up for the forming of the leading edge. The arrows show the way the blank is released prior to pressing: The MDF blocks press onto the pin-holders.

The leading edge and the spar for the rudder both have a length of approximately 130 cm. This is about as long as the ribs for large commercial aircraft rudders. Depending on the shape of the part to be formed, an active blankholder might be needed [4]. This means forces will be introduced into the laminate during forming to prevent the material from wrinkling in certain areas. In this case, however, an active blankholder was not needed. In order to hold and transport the blank a steel frame with mounted pins was used (see figure 16). The frame was clamped into the existing transfer clamps of the press. Mounted to the upper table of the press are MDF blocks, which press onto the steel pin-holders of the frame, prior to the forming step. As a result, the material could deform without any blankholder forces. The same principle was used to form the spar.

To the spar, extra layers of carbon reinforced PEI were added to the areas where the hinges of the rudder would be attached. Extra strength and stiffness can be added to areas where stress concentrations occur. The extra layers might be spot welded prior to rubber forming with an ultrasonic pistol to position them precisely. The result is shown in figure 17. The local reinforcements remained positioned accurately after rubber forming.

Figure 17: Spar with added layers where the hinges will be fixed. The spar is being connected to the flanges of ribs 2-6 with ultrasonic welding here.

CONCLUSIONS

It was found that both positive and negative rubber forming have their advantages and disadvantages and that the choice depends on the type of application. Small structural ribs can be formed with the net-shape forming method, so that trimming after forming is not required anymore.

Considering tooling it must be concluded that the production of suitable rubber moulds is rather difficult, because the shape of the rubber mould is not exactly the same as the product shape. However, a few design rules, based on visual inspection of the products, are given. One is the use of ridges in sharp corners that otherwise would not be pressurized. For the fixation of the rubber in case of negative forming, it can be concluded that aluminium should be used rather than MDF, since the MDF sometimes broke or bended due to the high forming forces.

The parts were all successfully integrated in the assembly. Therefore, it can be concluded that rubber forming is a very good and cost-efficient technique to form structural parts for large monolithic thermoplastic movables like rudders. By using advanced welding techniques like resistance and ultrasonic welding for the assembly, thermoplastics have a high potential replacing existing metal or thermoset structures in the future.

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